

Deep Learning based Diagnosis of Jaw Cyst using Hematoxylin and Eosin -Stained Incisional Biopsies Microscopic Images

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Abstract.

Clinicians and pathologists may find it difficult to distinguish between a radicular cyst, dentigerous cyst, and odontogenic keratocyst due to their complex microscopic diagnostic distinction. The development of computer-aided diagnostics for cyst identification leads to more accurate and timely diagnosis while reducing false positives and negatives. This research aimed to develop a deep learning based automated jaw cyst diagnosis system that recognizes Odontogenic Keratocyst (OKC), Dentigerous Cyst (DC) and Radicular Cyst (RC) based on Hematoxylin and Eosin-Stained images. Here 54 Odontogenic Keratocyst (OKC), 23 Dentigerous Cysts (DC), and 20 Radicular Cysts (RC) patient's data were examined using a 40× magnification microscope. In this case, two stains were isolated, and convolutional layers were used to extract attributes from each stain image. These attributes were concatenated and relevant ones were selected by Relief F. Dense layer was used for classification. Obtained an accuracy of 95% on test dataset.

Keywords: Convolutional Neural Network, Deep Learning, Dentigerous Cyst, Odontogenic Keratocyst, Radicular Cyst.

1. Introduction

Radicular cysts are usually asymptomatic unless they become infected or grow large enough to cause swelling or pressure on surrounding structures. Dentigerous cysts Symptoms may include swelling, displacement of adjacent teeth, or occasionally pain if the cyst becomes infected. odontogenic keratocyst (OKC)s may be asymptomatic or present with swelling, pain, or cortical expansion of the jawbone [1]. Medical diagnostics could be greatly enhanced by machine learning approaches, which can reduce physician burdens and increase precision, reproducibility, and speed. Deep learning algorithms have been created in the field of histopathology that can execute tasks like cysts diagnosis in a manner comparable to that of expert pathologists. Nevertheless, few algorithms have been clinically implemented despite these encouraging results, making it difficult to strike a balance between optimism and hype for these novel approaches

[2-9]. Graph convolutional neural network based object detection was used on immunostained images of lymphoma cancer patients [10]. Cell detection could be accomplished with high accuracy in phase contrast images [11]. For biomedical research, deep learning-based microscope image analysis is very important [3].

2. Dataset Description

There were 104 formalin-fixed (10% buffered) paraffin-embedded biological specimens for OKCs, DCs, and RCs in the archives of the Faculty of Dental Sciences, Department of Oral Pathology, Ramaiah University of Applied Sciences. Hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) were then applied to 4-micron thick sections. There is an Ethics Committee at Ramaiah University of Applied Sciences (Registration Number EC-20211/F/058) that has approved the research. An Olympus BX53 research microscope, Jenoptik digital camera, and Gryphax imaging software were used for data acquisition. Images of tissue samples were taken manually at 40x magnifications and had a resolution of 3840 x 2160 pixels (px). Because pathology specimens vary from case to case, 30 images/slides could not be kept consistent. Images that were manually taken were annotated by a professional pathologist. As Keratocyst have distinct histologic appearances, including parakeratinised squamous lining epithelium composed of five to eight layers, jaw cysts were initially divided into OKC, DC and RC by standard diagnostic criteria. 70% of the dataset was used as a training set, with the remaining 15% used as a validation set and the remaining 15% as a test set as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Dataset Description

Class	OKC	DC	RC
Train	588	444	449
Test/Validation	126	96	94

3. Method

In the proposed method the microscopic images of RC, DC and OKC were resized to 512 x 512. In pre-processing step, the suggested design aimed to separate the H&E stain from the tissue images as shown in Fig 1. A custom CNN model was created and trained on these datasets to find the histopathological properties that separate OKC, DC, and RC. The developed CNN model was trained on H stain and E stain separately to extract the features and these features were concatenated as shown in Fig 2. A feature selection algorithm was applied on the extracted features. Later a dense layer was used to predict RC, DC or OKC. The model was then trained using Optimizer and Activation functions. The model obtained has a validation accuracy of 96% and a test accuracy of 95%. The CNN algorithm retrieved the characteristics of the H&E stains effectively and helped to predict the class properly in most cases.

Fig. 1. Workflow of the research

Fig. 2. Visualization of the transformed Images: (a) Represents the original RGB image (1) Odontogenic Keratocyst (2) Dentigerous Cyst (3) Radicular Cyst (b) Represents the H-stained image of the original image (c) Represents the E-stained image of the original image

The custom convolutional neural network had eight convolutional layers as shown in Fig 3. In the first two layers the kernel was 3x3 with depth of 32, the resulted feature maps had the higher abstract of the microscopic images with 508X508 with depth of 32. Batch normalization was performed to reduce the sensitivity over initial weights and to increase the speed of learning. These feature maps were passed through max pooling with 2x2 window and stride 2 to obtain the feature maps of size 254X254 with depth of 32. Max pooling layers served for dimensionality reduction. Similarly, six more convolutional layers were used to extract more intricate details of the microscopic images alternating with max pooling layers. Finally, the obtained features from each stain was 200,704. After concatenation the features were 401,408. Relief feature selection works on estimating the differences with feature values of the neighbor instance pairs. Relief feature selection works on estimating the differences with feature values of the neighbor case pairs. With the same class, if the feature value difference in the neighboring case pair, then the feature score decreases. Similarly, vice versa is true, if the feature value difference in the neighboring case pair exists and does not belong to the same class. Only 30 important features were chosen and fed to the dense layer with 30 neurons in the input layer and two neurons in the output layer.

Fig. 3. Custom CNN Model

4 Results and Discussions

In this study, when trained with the activation function ReLU and the SGD optimizer for 100 epochs with a batch size of 16, our customized model outperformed all other combinations of Optimizers and Activation function. Figure 4 shows that after a hundred epochs, the validation accuracy is 96% and the test accuracy is 95%.

(a)

(b)

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.96	0.91	0.93	94
1	0.94	0.96	0.95	96
2	0.96	0.98	0.97	126
accuracy			0.95	316
macro avg	0.95	0.95	0.95	316
weighted avg	0.95	0.95	0.95	316

(c)

Fig. 4. Results of Experiment : (a) Accuracy Curve (b) Loss Curve (c) Classification Report (d) Confusion Matrix

Final Model Test and predicted result visualization using Customized CNN: The images are predicted using the best model obtained as shown in **Fig 6**

In OKC histopathology, the most significant diagnostic features include thick epithelium, five to six layers of continuous basal cells, also called tombstone formation, and differentiation between epithelium and connective tissue. A further distinguishing feature of DC is that it has a thin epithelium layer with 2-3 layers of randomly scattered basal cells, while RC has a barely discernible epithelium layer that penetrates into connective tissue. Often, DCs are misdiagnosed as OKCs because their epithelial layers

thicken when they become inflammatory. In this class, there is a high degree of variability, making automated processing challenging. Histopathology images can be classified automatically using deep learning techniques. Pathologists can eliminate arbitrary manual examination of tissues under a microscope by automating digitized pathological image categorization, eliminating analytical variances involved in manual inspection. Table 2 shows the comparison of the proposed model with state of art methods

Fig. 6. Visualization of Test Images and Predictions Result

Table. 2. Comparison with state of art methods

Model	Recall	Precision	F1-Score	Accuracy
Standard convolution neural network (CNN)	0.85	0.85	0.83	0.83
VGG19	0.74	0.82	0.74	0.75
Standard ViT	0.94	0.85	0.89	0.90
Proposed model	.95	0.95	0.95	0.95

5 Conclusion

The tissue specimens of RC, DC and OKC stained with hematoxylin and eosin were collected into a dataset. A computer aided diagnosis system for recognizing RC, DC and OKC was developed. This will enable faster diagnosis and can lead to reduced waiting times for patients and quicker initiation of treatment. Brings in objectivity by ruling out subjectivity and reduces inter and intra laboratory diagnosis report variations. This system can be used in mass screening.

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Disclosure of Interests The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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